

Effect of Training and Career Development on Employee Performance: Moderating Effect of Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

Purpose: *This study's primary purpose is to explore the effect of training and career development on the employee performance of the executives of the private banks in the Colombo district. In addition, the study focuses on the moderating effect of job satisfaction of employees in examining the relationship of training and career development with employee performance.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The study employed a quantitative study, whereby questionnaires were issued to examine the objectives of the study. The data for the current study were collected from 150 executives of private banks in the Colombo area. The mean, standard deviation, correlation analysis and hierarchical regression analysis were used as the statistical tools to analyze the data.*

Findings: *In this research, the authors reviewed that training and career development have a significant positive impact on employee performance. Furthermore, the results indicated that the job satisfaction of the employees moderated the effect of training and career development on job performance, which is a strategic mechanism to enhance the job performance of the selected sample. This study contributes to filling literature gaps and helps employers to enhance the job performance of the employees in the organization.*

Limitations: *The study population was limited to the finance sector in the Colombo district and the study is cross-sectional. Further, the study did not test any other variables as the moderating variables also created a limitation in the study.*

Keywords: *Training, Career Development, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance*

Introduction

Lifelong learning is showcased as an essential coping strategy to sustain in the changing business world. The business world rapidly changes on a regular basis, necessitating the continuous development of employee skills, attitudes, knowledge and capabilities in order to improve job performance, growth, and remain competitive (Amin et al., 2013); therefore, organizations make investments in human capital. Human capital is the prime asset and source of competitive advantage, success, and growth for the organization (Kaye & Jordan-evans, 2000). Efforts to improve employees' competencies through mentoring and coaching are inevitably expected to evolve the career path in line with the development of an organization (Harlie, 2011). Career development is strengthening their ability to work or improving a person's ability to work to attain their desired career (Rival, 2009). Also, career development is expected by every employee get to motivate them to work well (Afiyati, 2018). Career development can be explained as a continuous process in which the individual strives to achieve customized career planning and workplace conditions through individual effort (Priyono, Chandra & Ariana, 2016). Hence, organizations give more attention to their employees, working on keeping them satisfied and engaged to create a high-performance organization.

The performance management system was implemented as a management reform to resolve and address organizational performance (Sharif, 2002). The attainment of something or indeed operational effectiveness is referred to as performance. In an organization, performance is realized at the organizational, process, and individual levels and the interrelationships between these will define the organization's vantage points (Tahir, Yousafzai, Jan, & Hashim, 2014). According to Marihot (2007), job satisfaction indicates the degree to which individuals feel positively or negatively about various aspects of their job tasks. Each person has a different level of satisfaction based on the value system that he/she adheres to. Extended amount of time through training practice, and training is more efficient for the level of employee performance.

There have been few studies that have shown a significant association between training, career development and employee performance with the moderating variable of job satisfaction in the literature (Keomorakath & Fendy, 2021). Especially, researchers have not focused on the current research model in the Sri Lankan context, especially in the Banking sector. Therefore, the empirical gap in the literature motivates the researcher to look into the company's training, career development, work satisfaction, and staff performance. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of training and career development on employee performance with the moderation of job satisfaction. Thus the objectives of the current study are as follows;

1. To investigate the levels of training, career development, employee performance and job satisfaction among executives of private banks in the Colombo district
2. To investigate the impact of training and career development on employee performance among executives of private banks in the Colombo district
3. To investigate the moderating effect of job satisfaction on the effect of training and career development on employee performance among executives of private banks in the Colombo district

Literature Review

Training

An individual's training is the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies required to execute a given work or employment. According to McGhee (1996), training can thus be defined as a planned and systematic effort by management aiming at changing employee behavior in a manner that would meet organizational goals. Training is a process of shaping and equipping individuals by increasing their skills, talents, knowledge, and behavior so that work can be conducted more quickly, effectively, and reasonably (Ichsan, 2020). According to Cole (2002), training is one factor that many organizations evaluate when attempting to progress personnel and issue promotions. Indeed, employee quality and continuous improvement of skills and productivity through training are now widely recognized as critical components in assuring the long-term survival and profitability of small firms, as well as creating a corporate culture that encourages continuous learning (McKenna & Beech, 2002). Employees will gain specialized knowledge and

be able to train skills that can later be applied in the workplace if they are given training (Adnyani & Dewi, 2019a).

Career Development

Career development is the result of an individual's career planning and the organization's supply of support and opportunities, which should ideally be a collaborative effort. Growth, continual attainment, and use of one's talents are all development examples. Desimone (2002), defined career development as an ongoing process through which an individual goes through a series of stages, each characterized by a relatively unique set of issues, themes and tasks. Career development is an essential part of employee growth and organizational effectiveness because when employees are well developed and equipped with the right skills, competencies, knowledge and resources to grow, this affects not only the employee, but also the institution and the country's economy. Further, career development is explained as an ongoing process in which people advance through a succession of stages, each of which is marked by a distinct set of difficulties, themes, and duties (Dizaho, Salleh, & Abdullah, 2016). Researchers suggest that training program in mentoring, coaching, orientation among others is needed to improve a person's career (Dona, Amaratunga, & Haigh, 2006). A person's career development could be concerned with a sequence or series of jobs held throughout their lives.

Employee Performance

The concept of work performance in organization has been subjective to the changes over the past years with the dynamism of the organizational environment. Employee performance generally refers to the amount of output generated from an employee's job execution over time in an organization. According to Oluseyi and Ayobami (2009), employee performance is related to the willingness and openness of an individual to try and achieve new things in their job. The performance of the job can be characterized by a person while carrying out his job. Job performance can also be defined as behaviors and activities to achieve organizational goals (Al-Omari & Okesheh, 2017). Further it is a human behavior that is an important factor in the evaluation of individual work efficiency.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is one of the most researched phenomena in the domain of human resource management and organizational behavior. It is commonly defined as a “pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences” (Schneider & Snyder, 1975; Locke, 1976). According to Kalisky (2007), job satisfaction is a worker’s sense of achievement and success on the job. It is generally perceived to be directly linked to productivity as well as to personal well-being. It implies doing a job one enjoys, doing it well and being rewarded for one’s efforts. Shukla and Singh (2016), simplified the definition of job satisfaction by stating it is an employee’s degree of content with his/her job. Job satisfaction further implies enthusiasm and happiness with one’s work and it is the key ingredient that leads to recognition, income, promotion, and the achievement of other goals that lead to a feeling of fulfillment.

Testing Hypotheses

Training plays a particular role in accomplishing an organizational goal by combining the interests of the organization and the employees (Afroz, 2018). The researchers discovered a robust link between employee training and employee performance. Caroline and Susan (2014) discovered that education and training influence work performance at Kenya State University and that work performance positively impacts employee performance. Other research findings also indicate a link between training and employee performance (Triasmoko et al., 2014). The study's overall findings indicate that training and development activities carried out in an organization have a direct impact on job satisfaction and performance (Khan, Mushtaq & Naz, 2020). Training will assist employees in mastering information, skills, habits, a sense of self-worth, and confidence, allowing them to perform efficiently and increase the organization's performance (Keomorakath & Fendy, 2021).

H1: There is a significant effect of training on employee performance

The function of leaders in career development and the role of feedback on career development are two indicators that play an important role in career development and are supported by the human resources department. According to studies, employees link their performance to training,

implying that training and development boost employee performance, resulting in job satisfaction (Ampomah, 2016). Employee performance is positively influenced by competency, training and education, and career development (Mardiyah & Purba, 2019). According to Silaban, Handaru, and Saptono (2021), career development has little effect on organizational commitment, but has a favourable and considerable effect on employee performance. Cedaryana et al. (2018) found that career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

H2: There is a significant effect of career development on employee performance

Job satisfaction, according to Ivancevich (1976) and Winda, Nayati, and Arik (2017), relates to an individual's overall attitude about their job. Employees who are happy with their jobs will bring a positive attitude to their jobs. A person who is content with his or her employment has a good attitude toward it, whereas one who is unsatisfied with it has a negative attitude toward it. As a result, in the case of job satisfaction, the connection between projected and actual performance was attenuated. Job happiness has been discovered as a modulator of the training-employee performance relationship (Keomorakath & Fendy, 2021). This was consistent with the findings of Ivancevich (1976) and Winda et al. (2017), who found that employee job satisfaction was regulated by training and employee performance.

H3: Job satisfaction will moderate the relationship between training and employee performance.

H4: Job satisfaction will moderate the relationship between career development and employee performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

(Source: Keomorakath & Fendy, 2021)

Methodology

The study has used a **deductive** approach as it has created the hypothesis based on a literature review and confirmed whether the hypotheses could be accepted or rejected. The research strategy used for the current study was a **survey**, as it involves collecting data with the use of a questionnaire to achieve the objectives, and a **cross-sectional study** was the time horizon for the current study. The sample population of the study comprises executives of four banks in the Colombo district, that is, 178 individuals. Out of this, a sample of 150 respondents was selected from the study population. The primary data were collected through an administrative-structured questionnaire to test the hypotheses.

The scales used in the current study are based on a 5-point Likert scale, which shows a range from 5 to 1, where 5= strongly agree and 1=strongly disagree. The questionnaire for training (4 items) was adapted from Bohlander and Snell (2010), and career development (8 items) was adapted from Winda et al. (2017) and Arifin et al. (2020). The dependent variable of the study; employee performance (5 items) was measured using the questionnaire adapted from Chua, Ng, Tan, Teoh, and Wong (2013).

Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation tools were used to analyze the level of independent, moderating, and dependent variables of the study. With the results of the normal distribution, the author decided to select parametric techniques to conduct the research. **Multivariate regression analysis** was used as the statistical tool to examine the impact of training and career development on the employee performance of the sample. Meantime, **hierarchal regression analysis** was used to examine the moderating effect of job satisfaction on both relationships between training and employee performance; career development, and employee performance among the selected sample.

Data Analysis

Testing Research Model

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The reliability of the instrument is measured using Cronbach's Alpha. It measures the internal consistency of the instrument and determines whether the scale is reliable. Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient (CAC) is calculated for statements of each dimension based on a complete set of data collected. Overall CAC values for independent, moderate and dependent variables are above 0.5 (see Table 1), indicating that the measurements used in the current study are acceptable.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Variable	CAC Value
Training	0.835
Career Development	0.822
Job Satisfaction	0.847
Employee Performance	0.780

(Source: Survey Data)

The researcher has used Bartlett's measure test to understand the validity of the variables. The KMO value kept on changing among 0 and 1 where if the value exceeds 0.5 then the collected data is satisfied the requirements (Kaizer, 1994). In the current study, KMO values of the current study exceed 0.5 (KMO = 0.737) and Bartlett's test values are significant as p- value is <0.5 (sig = 0.000), the data is valid to carry forward further analysis.

Data Presentation of Personal Information

The current study consists of personal information in relation to demographic factors of 150 respondents such as gender, age, marital status and highest academic qualification of the selected sample from executives in the private banks in the Colombo district.

According to survey data out of 150 respondents, 68.7% are males and females constitute 31.3% share of the total sample. It indicates a higher percentage of male respondents. Age distribution of 150 respondents were categorized into six age categories 18-25, 26-35, 36-45, 46-55 and above 56, consist with 30%, 30%, 20%, 13.3% and 6.7% respectively. Furthermore, this shows that 60% of the sample belongs to the age above 35 years. Further, among those 150 respondents, 58% of the selected academic staff are single and only 42% of them are married. The distribution of the

highest academic qualifications depicts that among the 150 respondents, 24% and 48.7% of the respondents are having G.C.E. O/L and G.C.E. A/L qualifications respectively, while 21.3% of the respondents are bachelor's degree holders and 4.7% respondents have other educational qualifications.

Descriptive Analysis

Mean and Standard Deviation

Table 2: Overall Mean and Standard Deviation Values

Variables/ Dimensions		Mean	Standard Deviation
Independent Variables	Training	4.11	0.760
	Career Development	3.80	0.714
Moderator	Job Satisfaction	4.10	0.743
Dependent Variable	Employee Performance	4.19	0.712

(Source: Survey Data)

The mean of the selected sample's independent variables such as training and career development as 4.11 and 3.80 with a standard deviation of 0.760 and 0.714 respectively. Meantime, mean value of the moderate variable; job satisfaction is 4.10 and the data is deviated around mean value of 0.743. Further, the mean value of the dependent variable, employee performance is as 4.19 with a standard deviation of 0.712. Meaning average response towards each variables indicate high level of independent, moderate and dependent variable. Maximum and minimum values are 1 and 5 for all the variables saying that the respondents widely rated for all the questions in the questionnaire with the provided scale.

The Effect of Training and Career Development on Employee Performance

The study used the multivariate regression analysis to measure the effect of training and career development on employee performance of the selected sample. Regression analysis figure out the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. If the p value is less than the alpha

value of 0.05 then, it is significant in statistical term. Whereas, if the p value is greater than 0.05 then, it is not significant in statistical term.

Table 3: Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics		
					R Square Change	F Change	Sig. F Change
1	0.785	0.616	0.610	0.337	0.616	117.746	0.000

Dependent Variable EP

Predictors: (Constant), T, CD

(Source: Survey Data)

According to table 3, statistics R square is reported as 0.616 which means training and career development have a 61.6% impact on employee performance of the selected sample. Moreover, the adjusted R square indicates that 61% of the variation in employee performance could be explained by training and career development identified in the current study. The significant value of the ANOVA table, sig=0.000 depicts the significance of the regression model.

Table 4: Coefficient of Simple Linear Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.438	0.184		3.718	0.000
Training	0.335	0.047	0.416	1.408	0.000
Career Development	0.352	0.041	0.495	2.254	0.000

Dependent Variable: Employee performance

(Source: Survey Data)

According to table 4, statistics significance of the employee training variable t value is 0.000 ($P < 0.05$), whereas it is concerned as significant in a statistical term. Thus, based on evidence it could be concluded that training has a significant positive impact on employee performance. Further, the coefficient value ($B = 0.335$), depicts that when training increases with a value point of one, then the performance of employees will also increase by a value of 0.335. The Hypothesis

regarding the impact of training on employee performance of executives in the selected private banks is stated below and hence, the H1 of the study can be accepted.

H1: There is a significant effect of training on employee performance

The statistical significance of the t value is 0.000 ($P > 0.05$). Regression results reports the B value of employee individual career mapping as 0.352, which means if employee career development increases by one-point employee performance will increase by 0.352. Thus, based on evidence it could be concluded that employee career development has a significant positive impact on employee performance. Hence, H2 can be accepted.

H2: There is a significant effect of career development on employee performance

Moderating Effect of Job Satisfaction on the effect of Training and Career Development on Employee Performance

Hierarchical regression analyses were used to investigate the moderating effect of job satisfaction on the effect of training and career development on employee performance.

Table 5: Moderating Impact of Job Satisfaction on the relationship between Training and Employee Performance

	Model 1			Model 2		
	t-value		p- value	t-value		p- value
T	10.481		.000	8.377		.000
T x JS				3.928		.000
R2 Change		0.426	.000		0.481	
F Change		109.854			15.426	
Sig F Change		0.000			0.000	

(Source: Survey Data)

Table 5 shows the results of the hierarchical regression analysis which is used to measure the moderate impact of job satisfaction on the relationship between training and employee performance. In the hierarchical regression analysis, training (T) was used for Block 1, and the moderate variable, job satisfaction used for Block 2. The results of the hierarchical regression

analysis (R2change= 0.481, F change= 15.426, Sig. F Change= 0.000) identified that job satisfaction moderately impacts the relationship between training and job performance.

Table 6: Moderating Impact of Job Satisfaction on the relationship between Career Development and Employee Performance

	Model 1			Model 2		
	t-value		p- value	t-value		p- value
CD	11.728		.000	10.098		.000
CD x JS				4.598		.000
R2 Change		0.482	.000		0.547	
F Change		137.549			21.144	
Sig F Change		0.000			0.000	

(Source: Survey Data)

Table 6 shows the results of the hierarchical regression analysis which is used to measure the moderate impact of job satisfaction on the relationship between career development and employee performance. In the hierarchical regression, analysis career development (CD) was used for Block 1, and the moderate variable, job satisfaction used for Block 2. The results of the hierarchical regression analysis (R2change= 0.547, F change= 21.144, Sig. F Change= 0.000) identified that job satisfaction moderately impacts the relationship between career development and employee performance.

Discussion

This study aims to examine the moderating effect of job satisfaction in between the effect of training and career development on employees' job performance among the executives in the selected private banks in the Colombo district in response to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The results of the study aided theoretical implications towards the previous findings of the literature. The findings of this study show that employees' performance will be increased if employees get exposure to quality training and career development programs. The results of the selected sample highlighted that career development has the highest impact on employee performance compared to the effect of training. This showcases that the opportunities given for employees to climb up their career ladder have more impact on their performance. These findings of the study were supported by the findings of a previous study by Keomorakath and Fendy (2021),

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where the authors indicated that career development has predicted 29.1% of variance in employee performance while training has explained 11.2% variance in employee performance. Similarly, the findings of the current study were consistent with Winda et al., (2017) and Arifin et al., (2020). Further, the findings show that job satisfaction significantly moderated the relationship between training, career development and employee performance. The findings suggest that job satisfaction can enhance the favourable link between training, career development and employee performance and the findings are consistent with the literature (Keomorakath & Fendy, 2021; Paramita et al., 2020). The organization should develop strategies to enable its employees to have a favorable working environment without difficulties. And also family members should play important role in assisting employees in declining the burden of household duties by helping out each other.

Recommendations and Limitations

The study results show that training and development significantly affect employee performance with the moderation of job satisfaction. Hence, HR professionals are challenged to enhance organizational performance by adequately investing in their human capital. Management needs to identify the gaps in employee performance and provide customized training programs to get the best outcome. HR professionals should develop programs that can improve employees' competencies, with appealing packaging such as the best innovative ideas, best employee, training and education relevant to the workplace's success. Evaluating the outcomes of various tasks to ascertain how far an individual has progressed is needed for effective and sustainable organizational improvements. Further, giving opportunities and mentoring employees to climb the career ladder would also affect the employee's high performance. Therefore, arranging special career planning and developing stalls with mentors would greatly impact employee performance for a competitive edge.

The study population of limited to the executives of the private banking sector in the Colombo district, where it is a limitation to generalize the findings. Conducting future qualitative studies with different samples would provide deep insight into the research model.

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